

AGRIBALKAN 2021

III. BALKAN AGRICULTURAL CONGRESS

**29 AUGUST – 01 SEPTEMBER 2021,
EDIRNE, TURKEY**

III. Balkan Agriculture Congress, Edirne, Turkey, 29 August - 1 September, 2021

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In Trakya University Balkan Congress Center, Edirne, Turkey

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EVALUATION OF THE CONTENT OF PHENOLIC COMPOUNDS AND ANTIOXIDANT POTENTIAL OF WHITE MULBERRY FRUITS AND PEKMEZ

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ABSTRACT

Mulberry fruits and pekmez are known for their protective, or therapeutic effect to human health. Pekmez is considered as energy source food containing concentrated nutrients, also in Albania is known as for many years it has been produced by traditional method. The study was conducted to evaluate the content of phenolic compounds and antioxidant potential of white mulberry fruits collected in Tirana region, and its product pekmez. Pekmez control sample was prepared without clarifier agents and no sugar, which was compared with other pekmez samples prepared with the aid of various clarifier agents (2% w/w): bentonite, gelatin, calcium carbonate, and samples with sugar added. The total phenolic content, flavonoids and antioxidant potential were evaluated for whole fresh fruit, juice, pomace and pekmez, and the study of influence of various clarifier agents on them. Based on results mulberry fruit had the total polyphenolic content 285.41 mg gallic acid equivalent/100 g of sample in fresh weight (f.w.), and was found 46.97% lower content in juice, whereas in pomace and pekmez was found a greater content (55.32 % and 41.23 %) compared to fresh fruit. Pekmez samples prepared with the aid of clarifier agents resulted to have a greater amount of phenolic content (0.27-30.00 %) compared to control samples. Total flavonoids content resulted 20.67 mg catechin equivalents/ 100 g f.w., juice had 69.55 % lower content, whereas pomace and pekmez had 44.06 % and 56.49 % greater content, also pekmez samples prepared with the aid of clarifier agents resulted to have a greater amount of flavonoids (10.18-87.19%) compared to control samples. Antioxidant activity evaluated with ABTS (2,2'-azino-bis(3-ethylbenzothiazoline-6-sulfonic acid) assay resulted from 158.06 to 170.66 mg ascorbic acid equivalent/ 100 g f.w. in pekmez samples, whereas the DPPH (2,2-diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl) assay resulted from 29.30 to 43.31 % of inhibition in pekmez samples. Based on study findings may be concluded that clarifier agents contributed positively, as a higher content of phenolic compounds and antioxidant potential resulted, and was in the order: control < sugared < bentonite < gelatin < calcium carbonate, where among clarifier agents calcium carbonate had a higher influence, which may be recommended to be utilized as beneficial for the pekmez production, and for its commercial importance.

Keywords: white mulberry, pekmez, clarifier agents, phenolic compounds, antioxidant potential

INTRODUCTION

White mulberry (*Morus alba* L.) belongs to the *Morus* genus of Moraceae family, and is native to Asia, which has been highly adaptable and well grown in Albania. Mulberry is dispersed extensively in diverse climatic and environmental circumstances ranging from tropical to temperate. Amongst all the species of genus *Morus* as *Morus alba* is a dominant species (Ercisli and Orhan, 2007).

The presence of valuable constituents in mulberry fruits makes the plant suitable to be utilized as a functional food useful to human health in addition to its basic nutritional function (Kadam, 2019). *Morus alba* has abundant phytochemicals, including phenolic acids, flavonoids, flavonols, anthocyanins, macronutrients, vitamins, minerals, and volatile aromatic compounds (Chen et al., 2021). Mulberry fruits are famous for their mouth-watering taste that makes it suitable to consume either in fresh or as an ingredient in value-added products, for culinary uses, and processed product forms such as juices, syrups, liquors, molasses, jams, wines, natural dyes, beverages, or dehydrated fruits (Gundogdu et al., 2011).

Pekmez is one of the popular and food products produced by concentration of fruit juice of mulberry. It is rich in carbohydrates, minerals, some vitamins and antioxidants, and are energy storage and food source (Badem, 2018).

The aim of this study was to evaluate the content of total phenolic content, flavonoids and antioxidant potential of white mulberry (*Morus alba* L.) fruits collected in Tirana region for whole fresh fruit, juice, pomace and pekmez samples prepared with the aid of various clarifier agents (2% w/w): bentonite, gelatin, calcium carbonate, and with sugar added. The generated data of this study may serve for fruit processors, consumers and researchers.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

Mulberry fruits (*Morus alba*) were randomly collected in May-June 2021 in Tirana, Albania, and were transported immediately to the laboratory for further analysis and processing to pekmez. For preparation of pekmez samples was followed the flow diagram as in Figure 1.

Prior processing a pre-selection was done based on fruits maturity, shape, size, and color. Then fruits were washed and cleaned and a part of them was mixed with sugar (~8% w/w), which served for pekmez with added sugar preparation, and remained fruits were crushed, pressed to obtain fruit juice and pomace. Filtration of extracted juice was made with through muslin cloths, and clarifier agents 2% (w/w) bentonite, gelatin, calcium carbonate were mixed with filtered juice for clarification. Then the upper phase was collected, filtered again through a muslin cloths and transferred in an open pan for boiling, and during boiling, any foam produced was removed. This process last until the desired consistency of pekmez was obtained (min. 65-70°Brix). After pekmez samples were cooled, were packed and stored.

Samples were coded depend on the steps during processing or clarifier agent used, or sugar added: F=fresh fruit, JF= fruit juice, P/C= pomace from fresh fruit, PS=pomace from fruit with sugar, JB= juice with bentonite, JG= juice with gelatin, JCa= juice with calcium carbonate, and their respective precipitates P/B, P/G, P/Ca, C=pekmez with no added sugar or clarifier

mL 5% NaNO₂. After 5 min, 0.3 mL of 10% AlCl₃ solution was added and allowed to stand for another 6 min before 2.0 mL of 1 M NaOH was added, and the total volume was made up to 10 mL with distilled water. The solution was mixed completely and the absorbance level was measured spectrophotometrically versus prepared reagent blank at 510 nm using UV/Vis spectrophotometer Libra S22. A standard curve of the catechin was constructed ($y=0.0036x+0.0007$) and the results for TF were expressed as mg catechin equivalent (CE)/100 g FW.

Antioxidant activity was determined using ABTS (2,2'-azino-bis(3-ethylbenzothiazoline-6-sulfonic acid) radical scavenging assay according to Re et al., (1999). ABTS and potassium persulfate mixture was kept in the dark at room temperature for 16 h before use. For the analysis, the stock solution was diluted in aqueous methanol 80% (v/v) until the absorption at 734 nm reached 0.7 ± 0.02 . An aliquot (25 μ l) of sample was mixed with 975 μ l of ABTS reagent. A standard curve of the ascorbic acid was constructed ($y = -0.1641x + 0.7139$) and the results were expressed as mg ascorbic acid equivalents (AAE)/100 g FW.

The capacity of the prepared extracts to scavenge the free radical 2,2-diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl (DPPH \cdot) was carried out as described Yildirim et al., (2001). 0.1 mM DPPH radical solution in methanol was prepared, and then this solution was added to 280 μ L extracts of samples, till a final volume of 2mL. After incubation for 30 min in the dark, the absorbance was measured at 517 nm. Antioxidant activity was given as percent of inhibition, which was calculated with the equation:

$$Inhibition\% = \left(\frac{Abs_{Control} - Abs_{sample}}{Abs_{Control}} \right) * 100$$

The analyzes were performed at least in three replications, and were calculated as Mean values, \pm standard deviation.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Based on the study results mulberry fruit has the total polyphenolic content 285.41 mg gallic acid equivalent/100 g of sample in fresh weight (f.w.), and was found a lower content in juice (46.97%), whereas in pomace and pekmez was found a greater content (55.32 % and 41.23 %) compared to F samples (Figure 2). Juices with added clarifier agents resulted to have greater amounts of polyphenols compared to JF in amount 15.79% (JB), 19.92% (JG), and 22.26% (JCa).

Samples with sugar added resulted to have slightly lower amount of phenolic content in pomace as in PS was found 7.71 % lower compared to PC sample (377.22 mg GAE/100 g f.w.), whereas in precipitates of clarified juices were found greater amounts 6.86 % (PB), 7.14% (PG), and 8.18% (PCa) compared to PC sample.

In pekmez with sugar added was found 1.91 % (S) lower compared to C (434.08 mg GAE/100 g f.w.), whereas pekmez samples prepared with the aid of clarifier agents resulted to have a slightly greater amount of phenolic content 2.08% (B), 5.53% (G), and 17.16% (Ca) compared to C sample.

Figure 2. Total phenolic content in mulberry fruit, juice, pomace and pekmez samples

Results revealed that clarifier agents contributed positively, as a higher content of phenolic content was determined, and generally was followed the order for pekmez samples: sugared < control < bentonite < gelatin < calcium carbonate.

Total flavonoids content resulted in mulberry fruit 20.67 mg catechin equivalent/100 g of sample in fresh weight (f.w.), and was found a lower content in juice (69.55%), whereas in pomace and pekmez was found a greater content (44.06 % and 56.49 %) compared to F sample (Figure 3). Juices with added clarifier agents resulted to have greater amounts of flavonoids compared to JF 39.51% (JB), 41.14% (JG), and 48.73% (JCa).

Samples with sugar added resulted to have greater amounts of flavonoids content in pomace as in PS sample was found 59.3% greater compared to PC (29.78 mg CE/100 g f.w.), whereas in precipitates of clarified juices were found lower amounts 39.54% (PB), 23.8% (PG), and 17.37% (PCa) compared to PC sample.

In pekmez was found greater flavonoids in S sample (87.16 %) compared to C sample (32.35 mg CE/100 g f.w.), whereas pekmez samples prepared with the aid of clarifier agents resulted to have a slightly greater amount of flavonoids content 9.22% (B), 18.12% (G), and 26.22% (Ca) compared to C sample.

Figure 3. Total flavonoid content in mulberry fruit, juice, pomace and pekmez samples

Results revealed that clarifier agents contributed positively, as a higher content of flavonoids content was found, and generally was followed the order: control < bentonite < gelatin < calcium carbonate < sugared samples.

Antioxidant activity evaluated with ABTS assay resulted from 158.06 to 170.66 mg ascorbic acid equivalent/ 100 g f.w. of samples (Figure 4). Mulberry fruit had antioxidant activity 61.73 mg AAE/100 g f.w., and in juice was found to be lower (30.84%), whereas in pomace and pekmez was found to have a greater antioxidant activity (47.44% and 61.6 %) compared to fresh fruit. Juices with clarifier agents resulted with greater antioxidant activity compared to JF, 18.10% (JB), 20.90 % (JG), and 21.84% (JCa).

Samples with sugar added resulted to have lower antioxidant activity in pomace as PS was found 29.55% lower compared to PC (117.44 mg GAE/100 g f.w.), also precipitates from clarified juices had slightly lower antioxidant activity 2.46% (PB), 10.24% (PG), and 17.09% (PCa) compared to PC sample.

In pekmez with added sugar (S) was found 1.67 % lower compared to C (434.08 mg GAE/ 100 g f.w.), whereas pekmez samples prepared with the aid of clarifier agents resulted to have a slightly greater antioxidant activity 2.59% (B), 5.65% (G), and 5.81% (Ca) compared to C samples.

Figure 4. Antioxidant activity (with ABTS assay) of mulberry fruit, juice, pomace and pekmez samples

Antioxidant activity evaluated with DPPH assay expressed as % of inhibition resulted from 29.30 to 43.31 % of samples (Figure 5).

Figure 5. Antioxidant activity (with DPPH assay) of mulberry fruit, juice, pomace and pekmez samples

Antioxidant activity evaluated with ABTS and DPPH assays correlate well with each other and with determined phenolic content. Based on above results is notable that clarifier agents have a positive influence following the order: control < sugared < bentonite < gelatin < calcium carbonate.

CONCLUSIONS

This study clearly shows the potential of mulberry and pekmez to human health, as good sources of polyphenols 151.35-524.01 mg GAE/100 g f.w., flavonoids 6.29-60.54 mg CE/100 g f.w., antioxidant activity 42.69-170.66 mg AAE/100 g f.w. or 29.30-43.31 % of inhibition.

Based on results mulberry fruit had the total polyphenolic content 285.41 mg gallic acid equivalent/100 g of sample in fresh weight (f.w.), and was found 46.97% lower content in juice, whereas in pomace and pekmez was found a greater content (55.32 % and 41.23 %) compared to fresh fruit. Pekmez samples prepared with the aid of clarifier agents resulted to have a greater amount of phenolic content (0.27-30.00 %) compared to control samples. Total flavonoids content resulted 20.67 mg catechin equivalents/ 100 g f.w., juice had 69.55 % lower content, whereas pomace and pekmez had 44.06 % and 56.49 % greater content, also pekmez samples prepared with the aid of clarifier agents resulted to have a greater amount of flavonoids (10.18-87.19%) compared to control samples.

Based on study findings may be concluded that phenolic content, flavonoid content and antioxidant activity were found lower in juice, and higher in pomace compared to whole fresh mulberry fruit. In pekmez these substances were concentrated making pekmez as good source of natural antioxidant compounds.

Furthermore, clarifier agents contributed positively, as a higher content of phenolic content, flavonoid content and antioxidant activity were found and generally was followed the order: control < sugared < bentonite < gelatin < calcium carbonate. Among clarifier agents calcium carbonate was noted to affect phenolic content and antioxidant activity positively, as greater amount were determined in samples with added calcium carbonate, which may be recommended to be utilized as beneficial for the pekmez production.

The generated data of this study may serve for fruit processors, consumers and researchers.

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